

GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF THE GANJA DIALECT OF THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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The syntactic structure of the Azerbaijani language emerged concurrently with the development of Turkish oral speech and has continued to evolve over the ages. Progress and advancements in the syntactic structure are intricately linked to the rich cultural heritage of our people. The historical roots of the Azerbaijani language's syntactic structure are ancient. Azerbaijani sentences exhibit a diverse range of structural elements. The presence of simple sentences, simple sentences with verbs, simple sentences with homogeneous constituents, as well as complex sentences—both in subordinate and subordinate—demonstrates that our language ranks among the world's most syntactically affluent languages.

Keywords: language, grammar, syntax, Ganja dialect.

The field of syntax within Azerbaijani linguistics has undergone significant refinement through extensive scholarly research. The syntactic structure of our language developed in parallel with the evolution of Turkish oral speech, persisting across the ages. Advancements in the syntactic structure are intricately linked to the intellectual depth of our people. As philosophers assert, language embodies the essence of thought, and its capacity to shape cognition plays a pivotal role in education by expanding one's vocabulary. The historical genesis of the syntactic structure of our language dates back to ancient times. Remarkably, there is no significant difference between the contemporary syntactic structure of Azerbaijani and the linguistic structure found in works like "Dada Gorgud," our older Bayati poetry, and folk songs. Azerbaijani sentences exhibit a rich variety of structural elements, encompassing simple sentences, those with verbs, simple sentences with homogeneous constituents, as well as complex sentences—both independent and subordinate. This diversity of syntactic structures positions our language among the world's most syntactically diverse languages. The study and examination of the syntactic structure of our language, however, are of relatively recent origin. For an extended period, the study of the syntactic structure of our language was confined to the scope of school grammar. The establishment of a comprehensive scientific syntax curriculum represents a more recent development. The emergence of textbooks from the 1950s onwards, delving into distinct facets of the Azerbaijani language and elucidating nuanced differences in syntactic units, paved the way for systematic scholarly exploration of syntactic structure. In this domain, the contributions of prominent scholars, including M. Shiraliyev, A. Damichizade, N. Hajiyeva, A. Abdulayev, Z. Taghizade, Y. Seyidov, H. Hasanov, Z. Budagov, K. Abdullayev, G. Kazimov, and H. Mirzazade, are irrefutable. The research endeavors of these individuals encompass vital aspects that transcend the conventional classification framework of syntactic progression, encompassing all facets and stages of linguistic activity and communicative discourse. M. Sh. Shiraliyev, in particular, conducted extensive investigations into the parallels and distinctions between contemporary Azerbaijani language dialects and the

grammatical and syntactic structures of both our dialects and the literary language. These inquiries have yielded valuable insights into numerous theoretical issues.

As is the case with the scrutiny of morphological phenomena, in the realm of syntactic analysis, the consideration of both commonalities and peculiarities within dialects, as well as diligent attention to exceptions and other variables, is imperative. All of these factors collectively contribute to fortifying a previously underexplored dimension within the study of Azerbaijani dialects and accents. The resolution of syntactic issues within the framework of our linguistic discourse serves to streamline the task of investigating dialects and regional accents. In this regard, the extensive historical record of the Azerbaijani literary language can provide invaluable assistance. Nonetheless, it is essential to approach the study of dialects and accents through a syntactic lens with caution, as rigid adherence to the grammatical norms of the literary language can lead to an unwarranted characterization of these linguistic variations as "incorrect speech." For instance, the arrangement of sentence constituents in colloquial language may appear more 'flexible' compared to literary language; however, this is merely an apparent observation. In truth, dialectal syntax exhibits its own underlying regularities. As these patterns are unveiled, the exploration of syntactic disparities becomes more manageable. Consequently, it is natural that the syntactic characteristics of dialects and accents exhibit certain deviations from the norms of the written language. Additionally, the use of repetition within a sentence can manifest in diverse ways, occasionally as a contextual necessity dependent on the communicative situation. When speakers believe that certain words may not be adequately understood by their audience or when they wish to emphasize the core aspect of their message, they may resort to repetition [3, 87].

The Ganja dialect of the Azerbaijani language stands as one of the oldest settlements of our civilization, preserving a wealth of linguistic attributes, particularly in terms of syntactic features. Within the realm of the modern Azerbaijani language, numerous historically evolved dialects and accents exist. The term 'dialect' finds its origin in the Greek 'dialectos,' signifying

'speech,' 'accent,' or 'vernacular.' In the scientific context, the term 'dialect' does not encompass all forms of 'speech.' Linguistics defines 'dialect' as a historically developed regional variation of a national language. In this vein, the Azerbaijani language boasts a multitude of historically developed dialects and accents. Each city, district, village, and vicinity possesses its distinct spoken language and dialect, and the Ganja region is no exception. The Ganja dialect falls within the Western dialect group. Azerbaijani linguists categorize Azerbaijani dialects into four main groups: Northern (comprising the Sheki dialect, Zagatala-Gakh, and Azerbaijani dialects in Dagestan), Southern (including Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Tabriz dialects, and the Iravan dialect), Eastern (encompassing Baku, Shamakhi, Guba dialects, as well as Mughan and Lankaran dialects), and Western (comprising Kazakh, Karabakh, Ganja dialects, and Irim dialects) [3, 87]. Dialects and the literary language, both integral components of a language, diverge from one another in terms of phonetic systems, grammatical structures, and vocabulary.

Literary language is established upon the principles of selecting and substituting elements from the national language. For instance, in order to standardize the vocabulary of the literary language, words are selected from the prevalent national language, certain terms from the national language are incorporated into the literary language's lexicon, while others are deemed unsuitable for literary use' [4, 44]. It is incumbent upon every cultured individual to acquaint themselves with the norms of the literary language and adhere to them. In the context of linguistics, the term 'dialect' refers to a type or variant of a language employed within a delimited geographical area. Dialects represent the spoken language of distinct regions and cities, distinguished by their unique characteristics, in addition to the features shared by all languages. The Ganja dialect, belonging to the Western dialect group, distinguishes itself from its peers through distinctive lexical, phonetic, morphological, and syntactic features.

The syntactic characteristics of the Ganja dialect can be generalized as follows:

In the Ganja dialect, all three types of determiner phrases are observable. The first type of determiner phrase is constructed without any suffixes on either side. Virtually all variations of the first-type determiner phrases are prevalent: a) Those with a noun on both sides: Examples include sentences such as "Mis düşbalan yaman ağır idi; Taxta öy heş vāx nəm olmaz," and so forth. b) Instances where the first part is a number and the second part is a noun: For instance, "Yasa xeylax adam getmişdi" and "Büyün dölmədə beş uşaq vardı," etc. c) Cases in which the first part is an adjective and the second part is a noun: As in "Məhlədə yaxşı şöytəli pitir," and similar expressions."

The second type of Determining phrases is processed by taking the first part without suffix, and the second part with a transformative suffix. Here the accusative case accepts the genitive case's attributive suffixes. "Sə:r məməkoy səbzili pişmiş varıydı; Cimciməli kalağayı həmişə lələnin üstündəydi" and so on.

Both sides of the third type of determinative phrases take transformative suffixes. In this type of determinative phrase, the first part indicates a concrete, individual object and takes the possessive case of the noun, and the second part takes the attributive suffixes. "Öyün aynası elə silkəyələndi ki, zəhrim yarıldı; Humayın törəməsi hamısından gəşəydi" etc.

In the Ganja dialect, there are instances where two attributive suffixes conjoin on the second side within the third type of determiner phrase. For instance, 'O dəlləy olsa da bir günüsü xoş keşmədi.'

Conversely, there are cases where no suffix appears on the first side, particularly in definite phrases where the first part is represented by pronouns. For example, 'Mən yazdığım kitabda yoxdur,' and 'Onnar ikisi də ləms adamdır.'

In addition to the first, second, and third types of phrases, the Ganja dialect also features compound phrases, such as 'İnta:sı çinar ağacının kölgəsi cımxır nəmiydi,' and 'Yaz göyärtisinin suyuğu bərəkətsiz olur.'

One of the distinguishing features that sets literary language apart from dialects and regional accents lies in the arrangement of words within sentences. In literary language, there is a predefined and generally adhered-to word order. This expected word order is typically mirrored in dialects and regional accents. However, in the Ganja dialect, this convention is occasionally breached. In the Ganja dialect, Subject, Object, and Adverb positions are placed after the Informative case, while the Determiner follows the determined word: a) The Subject follows the Informative case: Examples include sentences like 'Sə:r obaşdan gəldi çirtım' and 'Gejdənnən göəli yedi Namlet,' among others. b) The Object is positioned after the Informative case: Instances like 'İrvaham ertədən çatdı haman adna-ya' exemplify this phenomenon.

Diverse types of sentences find application in Azerbaijani dialects and regional accents. Notably, there exists a discernible variance in the treatment of interrogative sentences across dialects. In certain dialects, such as Baku, Nakhchivan, and partially Nukha, interrogative sentences are articulated without suffixes, relying solely on interrogative intonation. However, within the cluster of Western dialects, particularly exemplified by the Ganja dialect, it is established that interrogative sentences are predominantly constructed through the addition of interrogative suffixes -mı/-mi/-mu/-mü, with intonation playing a comparatively less frequent role. For instance, sentences such as '-O cüvəlləğini görüfsənmı?' and '-O dərədəlləyi sənün törəməndimi?' illustrate this prevalent pattern.

As evident, the syntactic characteristics of the Ganja dialect set it apart from both our other regional accents and dialects, as well as the literary language. Researchers bear the responsibility of meticulously documenting, describing and presenting the numerous grammatical and lexical phenomena found within dialects and accents. At times, it may be feasible to resolve certain dialectal phenomena within the 'framework' of the broader language, thereby enhancing clarity. Nevertheless, there are instances where such resolution remains elusive.

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